

M2.2 Collection of existing best-practices and indicators for research software

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Milestone M2.2 “*Collection of existing best-practices and indicators for research software*” aims at providing a landscape analysis of existing solutions around research software and obtaining Community input into the selection of standards and tags.

This document presents a compendium of existing best practices and indicators for research software within the ELIXIR infrastructure and its wider communities. It is designed to serve as a landscape overview, helping to identify and categorise resources that adhere to the FAIR principles—Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable—thus enhancing the reproducibility of life sciences data and the usability of research tools.

Here, we distinguish between best practices and resources to ensure clarity in our categorization. The document is structured into three main sections:

1. **Categorization Tags for Research Software:** this section outlines the methodology used for categorization, focusing on the tags derived from the Software Management Plans (SMPs) tailored for life science researchers. These tags, such as *Documentation*, *Interoperability*, and *Versioning*, are crucial to define the role and focus of the listed resources. They provide a consistent framework for evaluating the quality and functionality of research software.
2. **ELIXIR-Related Best Practices and Resources:** this section details best practices and resources specifically related to ELIXIR. Here, we categorise resources into Articles, Services/Platforms, and Training/Lessons. Each resource is evaluated against the established tags, ensuring a comprehensive understanding of their contribution to research software best practices.
3. **General Best Practices and Resources Outside of ELIXIR:** in this section, we highlight essential guidelines and resources from the broader scientific and software development communities. These practices offer valuable insights and recommendations that extend beyond the ELIXIR framework, promoting enhanced quality, accessibility, and sustainability of research software.

By clearly differentiating between indicators, ELIXIR-specific resources, and general best practices, this document aims to provide a curated, evolving repository that reflects ongoing advancements and community contributions. The feedback from the community will continually shape this resource, ensuring its relevance and applicability in the rapidly evolving landscape of research software.

Categorization Tags for Research Software

The following tags have been derived from the Software Management Plans (SMPs) outlined in the "[ELIXIR Software Management Plan for Life Sciences](#)"¹ (Alves et al. (2021) BioHackrXiv.org). These SMPs are thoughtfully aligned with the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles for research software, as articulated by [Barker et al. \(2022\)](#)². Developed specifically for life science researchers in the context of ELIXIR, these SMPs serve as a categorisation framework used to define the third set of indicators in STEERS [M2.1: Community Engagement Scoreboard](#)³.

The high-level tags presented here are designed to categorise and articulate the role and focus of each ELIXIR-related resource listed in the subsequent sections. By employing these tags, we aim to enhance clarity and facilitate the discovery of critical resources within the ELIXIR framework, thereby fostering a more robust ecosystem for research software management.

Table 1. List of tags and their descriptions with references (REF)

Tags	Description
<i>Documentation</i> ▾	Availability and quality of user and developer documentation, including API documentation, README files, and other supporting materials that help in understanding and using the software. REF: ELIXIR Software Management Plan for Life Sciences
<i>Interoperability</i> ▾	Ensuring the use of standard input/output formats and the registration of the software in relevant standards or data registries for compatibility and integration with other

¹ <https://doi.org/10.37044/osf.io/k8znb>

² <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01710-x>

³

https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1pzmhlqJgUVFkbVe3hck_SMke2vtiXuPdNBRvdUjIMSo/edit?gid=1677100523#gid=1677100523

	<p>systems.</p> <p>REF: ELIXIR Software Management Plan for Life Sciences</p>
Versioning ▾	<p>Ensuring the use of a version control system and whether versioning is applied to manage changes and updates to the software.</p> <p>REF: ELIXIR Software Management Plan for Life Sciences</p>
Accessibility/License ▾	<p>Ensures that the software is publicly accessible and specifies the type of license under which it is released.</p> <p>REF: ELIXIR Software Management Plan for Life Sciences</p>
Recognition ▾	<p>Ensuring the provision of citation information, persistent identifiers like DOIs, and registering the software in relevant, domain-specific registries to ensure proper credit is given.</p> <p>REF: ELIXIR Software Management Plan for Life Sciences</p>
Reproducibility ▾	<p>Ensuring that the software's functionality can be reliably reproduced by providing releases, defining dependencies, capturing the environment, and offering input/output examples.</p> <p>REF: ELIXIR Software Management Plan for Life Sciences</p>
Testing ▾	<p>Ensuring the description of the types of tests performed on the software, such as unit, integration, end-to-end, and regression testing. This includes confirming that existing functionality remains intact after changes, as well as providing sample data and parameters to support comprehensive testing practices.</p> <p>REF: ELIXIR Software Management Plan for Life Sciences</p>
Software Management ... ▾	<p>Ensuring the development of a software management development plan simplified for life science projects, focusing on accessibility and reusability while adhering to FAIR principles, aiding reproducibility, meeting funding</p>

	<p>requirements, aligning with community standards.</p> <p>REF: ELIXIR Software Management Plan for Life Sciences</p>
Sustainability ▾	<p>Ensuring the long-term maintenance and support of research software through ongoing development, community engagement, and strategies for continued usability and adaptation.</p> <p>REF: Top 10 metrics for life science software good practices⁴</p>
Portability ▾	<p>Ensuring that research software can be easily shared and executed across various computing environments by utilising self-contained virtual development environments. This approach allows for specific versions of programming language interpreters and dependencies to be included, facilitating seamless replication and use by other researchers, thus enhancing the software's usability and reproducibility in life sciences.</p> <p>REF: https://everse.software/RSQKit/virtual_dev_environments/#why-should-you-use-virtual-software-development-environments</p>

ELIXIR-Related Best Practices and Resources

ELIXIR provides a structured framework for best practices, tools, and training resources focused on enhancing the management and sharing of research software in the life sciences. These resources are here categorised into three main sections: *Articles*, *Services/Platforms*, and *Training/Lessons*. This organisation ensures that researchers, software developers, and stakeholders have access to standardised guidelines and practical tools to support sustainable and reproducible research practices. Resources listed here include, but are not limited to, those available in the [ELIXIR guidelines](#)⁵ webpage, providing standardised best practices and recommendations to support the management and sharing of life sciences data and resources.

⁴ <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.9206.1>

⁵ <https://elixir-europe.org/what-we-offer/guidelines>

Articles

The *Articles* section includes reports and guidelines addressing key challenges in research software development. Topics covered include the adaptation of FAIR principles to software, metrics for evaluating software sustainability, and recommendations for implementing best practices in software management. These articles serve as essential resources for understanding and improving the quality and usability of research software.

[Building Towards a Machine-Actionable Software Management Plan: A BioHackathon Europe 2023 Report](#)⁶

The report highlights activities and achievements related to machine-actionable Software Management Plans (SMPs) and the Software Management Wizard (SMW) during the ELIXIR BioHackathon Europe 2023. It focuses on simplifying SMP creation for sustainable and reproducible research within ELIXIR, aligning with initiatives like OpenEBench and FAIR4RS. The outcomes are available for immediate use and future refinement based on community feedback and advancements. Target audience: researchers and software developers in the ELIXIR network and beyond. [Documentation](#) ▾ [Interoperability](#) ▾ [Versioning](#) ▾ [Accessibility/License](#) ▾ [Recognition](#) ▾ [Reproducibility](#) ▾ [Software Management Plan](#) ▾

[Towards FAIR principles for research software](#)⁷

Application of the FAIR principles to research software, highlighting the need to adapt these principles, originally designed for data, to software. It aims to summarise current debates and propose community-agreed principles for FAIR research software, noting differences between software and data, and identifying areas requiring adaptation or new principles, particularly interoperability. The goal is to outline steps toward defining FAIR principles for research software. The target audience includes researchers, software developers, and stakeholders in the scientific community.

[Documentation](#) ▾ [Versioning](#) ▾ [Accessibility/License](#) ▾ [Recognition](#) ▾ [Reproducibility](#) ▾ [Software Management Plan](#) ▾ [Sustainability](#) ▾

[Top 10 metrics for life science software good practices](#)⁸

Set of community-driven metrics for evaluating good development practices to ensure software sustainability, reusability, and functionality. Unlike previous efforts, this initiative involves experts proposing practical, adoptable practices for their communities. The focus is on understanding, prioritising, and assessing the feasibility of these practices. Target audience: software developers and community experts.

[Documentation](#) ▾ [Interoperability](#) ▾ [Versioning](#) ▾ [Recognition](#) ▾ [Reproducibility](#) ▾ [Testing](#) ▾ [Software Management Plan](#) ▾ [Sustainability](#) ▾

[Four simple recommendations to encourage best practices in research software](#)⁹

Recommendations to encourage the adoption of existing software development best practices, which enhance the quality, reproducibility, and reusability of research software.

⁶ <https://doi.org/10.37044/osf.io/t94g8>

⁷ <https://doi.org/10.3233/DS-190026>

⁸ <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.9206.1>

⁹ <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.11407.1>

Aimed at developers, organisations, projects, journals, and funders, it promotes Open Source values to make research software more discoverable, reusable, and transparent with better quality and more sustainable research software.

[Documentation](#) ▾ [Interoperability](#) ▾ [Versioning](#) ▾ [Accessibility/License](#) ▾ [Recognition](#) ▾
[Testing](#) ▾ [Reproducibility](#) ▾ [Sustainability](#) ▾

[General guidelines for biomedical software development](#)¹⁰

Challenges in bioinformatics software development, often created by non-professional developers, which affects utility, quality, and clinical adoption. It proposes guidelines for improving biomedical software quality, efficiency, and usability by adopting new strategies and engaging end-users. The review also suggests open-source tools to support these development practices. Target audience: biomedical software developers and clinical researchers.

[Documentation](#) ▾ [Interoperability](#) ▾ [Versioning](#) ▾ [Accessibility/License](#) ▾
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[Perspectives on automated composition of workflows in the life sciences](#)¹¹

The article summarises a workshop on automating the composition of scientific workflows in life sciences, addressing the challenges of manual workflow assembly due to a lack of standards. It reviews past and current methods, technologies, and practices for semantic domain modeling and workflow automation. A key outcome is a six-stage workflow life cycle model and a roadmap for advancing automated workflow development, aiming for more robust, reusable, and sustainable workflows. Target audience: life science researchers and workflow developers.

[Documentation](#) ▾ [Interoperability](#) ▾ [Versioning](#) ▾ [Accessibility/License](#) ▾ [Recognition](#) ▾
[Reproducibility](#) ▾ [Testing](#) ▾ [Software Management Plan](#) ▾ [Sustainability](#) ▾ [Portability](#) ▾

[Recommendations for the packaging and containerizing of bioinformatics software](#)¹²

Recommendations by the BioContainers Community for producing standardised bioinformatics software containers and packages. These guidelines aim to enhance the discoverability, reusability, and transparency of bioinformatics software by ensuring compliance with rules and standards. The recommendations target developers, organisations, journals, and funders to improve the quality and sustainability of research software.

[Documentation](#) ▾ [Interoperability](#) ▾ [Versioning](#) ▾ [Accessibility/License](#) ▾ [Recognition](#) ▾
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[FAIR Principles for Research Software \(FAIR4RS Principles\)](#)¹³ (in collaboration with Research Data Alliance)

FAIR Principles for Research Software (FAIR4RS), adapted from the FAIR Guiding Principles to address software-specific characteristics like executability and versioning. Developed by the FAIR4RS Working Group through community consultations since 2019, these principles aim to enhance the sharing and reuse of research software. Maintained by

¹⁰ <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.10750.2>

¹¹ <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.54159.1>

¹² <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.15140.2>

¹³ <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00068>

the RDA Software Source Code Interest Group, the principles are open for feedback and updates via RDA plenary events. Target audience: researchers and developers interested in software management and stewardship.

[Documentation](#) ▾ [Interoperability](#) ▾ [Versioning](#) ▾ [Accessibility/License](#) ▾ [Recognition](#) ▾
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[Introducing the FAIR Principles for research software](#)¹⁴ (with contribution from ELIXIR)

Adaptation of the FAIR Guiding Principles to research software by the FAIR for Research Software (FAIR4RS) Working Group, creating the FAIR Principles for Research Software (FAIR4RS Principles). It highlights the role of FAIR in addressing challenges related to discoverability, quality, and sustainability of research software. The summary provides an overview of these principles, examples of their implementation, and aims to promote their adoption and impact in the research community. Target audience: researchers, organisations, and advocates of open science and FAIR practices.

[Documentation](#) ▾ [Interoperability](#) ▾ [Versioning](#) ▾ [Accessibility/License](#) ▾ [Recognition](#) ▾
[Reproducibility](#) ▾ [Software Management Plan](#) ▾ [Sustainability](#) ▾

[DOME: recommendations for machine learning validation in biology](#)¹⁵

DOME offers community-wide recommendations for reporting supervised machine learning analyses in biological studies. Its adoption aims to enhance the assessment and reproducibility of machine learning applications. The target audience includes researchers and practitioners in computational biology and machine learning.

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[Reproducibility](#) ▾ [Testing](#) ▾ [Software Management Plan](#) ▾ [Portability](#) ▾

[Ten simple rules for making a software tool workflow-ready](#)¹⁶

10 rules for developing research software that can be integrated into computational workflows, addressing the need to adapt standalone tools for use in complex data analysis pipelines. It emphasises adopting established engineering practices, such as continuous testing, to ensure software quality and compatibility. The guidelines aim to improve the usability and maturity of research tools within workflows and are intended for software developers across various fields. The target audience includes researchers and software developers involved in workflow management systems.

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Services/Platforms

The **Services/Platforms** section highlights various tools and platforms that facilitate the discovery and management of bioinformatics resources. This includes community-curated registries, frameworks for standardising software packaging, and platforms for managing and

¹⁴ <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01710-x>

¹⁵ <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-021-01205-4>

¹⁶ <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1009823>

sharing computational workflows. These services enhance the accessibility and usability of software tools, supporting researchers in their scientific endeavours.

[Bio.tools](#)¹⁷

- [Tools and data services registry: a community effort to document bioinformatics resources](#)¹⁸

Life sciences produce vast data sets crucial for advancements in health, agriculture, and the environment. Numerous databases and tools support these discoveries, but their documentation is scattered and inconsistent, making it difficult for scientists to find and use the best resources. ELIXIR supports a community-driven effort to create a comprehensive registry of bioinformatics resources. This registry, maintained by local curation and a network of partners, aims to standardise information dissemination. As of November 2015, it contains 1785 resources from 126 registrations, including 52 institutional and 74 individual contributors. The registry is available at [bio.tools](#), and community participation is encouraged.

[Documentation](#) ▾ [Interoperability](#) ▾ [Versioning](#) ▾ [Accessibility/License](#) ▾
[Recognition](#) ▾ [Reproducibility](#) ▾ [Software Management Plan](#) ▾ [Sustainability](#) ▾
[Portability](#) ▾

- [Community curation of bioinformatics software and data resources](#)¹⁹

The vast and rapidly growing array of bioinformatics resources presents a challenge for life scientists in selecting appropriate tools. To tackle this, the European Infrastructure for Biological Information supports a unified registry of bioinformatics tools and databases accessible through a single portal at [bio.tools](#). This initiative allows scientific communities, individual developers, and major research providers to describe and share their resources, enhancing accessibility and usability across the field.

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- [biotoolsSchema: a formalised schema for bioinformatics software description](#)²⁰

biotoolsSchema is an information model for standardising descriptions of bioinformatics resources, addressing the challenge of heterogeneous data analysis in life sciences. Developed through community workshops, it provides concise yet rich technical and scientific context, facilitating rapid adoption. Deployed in the bio.tools registry, it offers over 17,000 machine-readable and human-understandable descriptions, enhancing interoperability and reusability. This supports the FAIRness of research software, promoting open and reproducible developments in data-intensive sciences. The target audience includes life scientists and bioinformaticians.

[Documentation](#) ▾ [Interoperability](#) ▾ [Versioning](#) ▾ [Accessibility/License](#) ▾

¹⁷ <https://bio.tools>

¹⁸ <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkv1116>

¹⁹ <https://doi.org/10.1093/bib/bbz075>

²⁰ <https://doi.org/10.1093/gigascience/giaa157>

[Recognition](#) - [Reproducibility](#) - [Software Management Plan](#) - [Sustainability](#) - [Portability](#)

[OpenEBench](#)²¹

[Lessons Learned: Recommendations for Establishing Critical Periodic Scientific Benchmarking](#)²²

This article addresses the increasing dependence of life scientists on bioinformatics software and the critical need for effective benchmarking to ensure the reliability and reproducibility of scientific results. The authors emphasise the importance of community-driven efforts in establishing continuous benchmarking systems, such as [OpenEBench](#), which provide objective evaluations of bioinformatics tools. Key recommendations include ensuring interoperability through standardised data formats, promoting public accessibility of benchmarking results, and implementing clear documentation and testing protocols. The article advocates for a structured framework that fosters collaboration among developers, researchers, and funders, ultimately aiming to enhance the quality and performance of bioinformatics software in the life sciences.

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[Software Management Wizard](#)²³

The Software Management Plan (SMP) outlines the management lifecycle of software for a project, ensuring long-term accessibility and reusability. ELIXIR's SMP is tailored for life science researchers and adheres to FAIR principles, refined from community practices and feedback. It covers five software lifecycle stages: Getting Started, Construction, Application, Production, and Publication. Using the ELIXIR Software Management Wizard, you can create an SMP project, generate documents in various formats, and integrate with the FAIR Evaluator to pre-fill SMP questions based on FAIR assessments.

[Documentation](#) - [Interoperability](#) - [Versioning](#) - [Accessibility/License](#) - [Recognition](#) - [Testing](#) - [Software Management Plan](#) - [Sustainability](#)

[FAIRsoft - A practical implementation of FAIR principles for research software](#)²⁴

Challenges in reproducing and verifying computational components in Life Sciences research, often due to undocumented software. To improve software quality and sustainability, principles similar to FAIR Data Principles are proposed. Within ELIXIR, OpenEBench aims to provide a platform for scientific benchmarking and software quality observance. This proposal introduces a FAIR-like framework to assess software quality as a first step towards implementing an observatory in OpenEBench. The target audience includes researchers and software developers in Life Sciences.

[Documentation](#) - [Interoperability](#) - [Versioning](#) - [Accessibility/License](#) - [Recognition](#) - [Reproducibility](#) - [Testing](#) - [Sustainability](#)

²¹ <https://observatory.openebench.bsc.es/>

²² <https://doi.org/10.1101/181677>

²³ <https://smw.dsw.elixir-europe.org/wizard/>

²⁴ <https://doi.org/10.1101/2022.05.04.490563>

[BIP! Scholar](#)²⁵

[BIP! scholar: a service to facilitate fair researcher assessment \[arXiv 2205.03152\]](#)²⁶

BIP! Scholar is a platform that allows researchers to create profiles summarising their research activities, enrich them with contextual information, and highlight different aspects of their research careers. The platform aims to offer profiles that cover a wide range of research activities, going beyond scientific publications. It reports diverse lists of contributions made by the researchers and a variety of relevant indicators considering their roles in the respective activities. Research software is one of the research contribution types captured by the platform offering relevant indicators (e.g., on the code availability) and researchers have the opportunity to highlight the importance of the respective items providing custom narratives. The platform supports multiple ways to present researcher profiles, offering templates that focus on the responsible and inclusive presentation of researcher careers (e.g., narrative CV templates). Finally, profiles can be dynamically tailored by the viewer to facilitate the examination of a researcher's career according to specific topics, roles or types of activity that may be of interest.

[Recognition](#) - [Sustainability](#) - [Portability](#) -

[APICURON](#)²⁷

[APICURON: The platform to credit and acknowledge scientific contributions](#)²⁸

APICURON is a comprehensive database specifically developed to recognize and attribute credit to researchers by meticulously tracking and aggregating their contributions across various knowledge bases. The foundation of APICURON lies in its ability to monitor activities performed on digital objects accessible on the web, including datasets, proteins, and other related entities. While its current emphasis is on tracking curation activities, APICURON carries the potential to expand its scope to encompass a broader range of research assets generated across diverse platforms, thereby enhancing its utility and impact within the scientific community.

[Recognition](#) - [Sustainability](#) - [Portability](#) -

[WorkflowHub](#)²⁹

[WorkflowHub: a registry for computational workflows](#)³⁰

Online platform designed to help researchers and scientists manage, share, and discover computational workflows used in scientific research. It is particularly focused on supporting reproducibility and reusability of workflows across various domains, including bioinformatics, genomics, and environmental sciences.

It is a workflow repository that supports version control, standardised descriptions and FAIR aspects, it supports collaborative development, citation and integration with other platforms (Zenodo - for sharing, GitHub - for version control and bio.tools). It uses standards (such as schema.org to describe metadata about workflows).

It supports best practice in workflow development including reproducibility, transparency, ease of use and adaptation of existing workflows to meet their needs.

²⁵ <https://bip.imsi.athenarc.gr/scholar>

²⁶ <https://doi.org/10.1145/3529372.3533296>

²⁷ <https://apicuron.org/>

²⁸ <https://doi.org/10.1093/database/baab019>

²⁹ <https://about.workflowhub.eu/>

³⁰ <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2410.06941>

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[RO-Crate](#)³¹

[Packaging research artefacts with RO-Crate](#)³².

[RO-Crate Metadata Specification](#)³³

An RO-Crate is a [Research Object](#)³⁴ (or RO) formed of a collection of data (a crate) and a special ro-crate-metadata.json file which describes the collection.

The collection may contain any kind of research data - papers, data files, software, references to other research, and so on. It may be a folder full of files, an abstract grouping of connected references, or a combination of both.

The ro-crate-metadata.json file (also known as the RO-Crate Metadata Document) is a plain text file, readable by humans and machines, that includes metadata for each item within the collection - the authors, licence, identifier, provenance, and so on. Any folder can be turned into an RO-Crate by adding an ro-crate-metadata.json file.

Researchers can distribute their work as an RO-Crate to ensure their data travels with its metadata, so that key components are correctly tracked, archived, and attributed.

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[Galaxy](#)³⁵

[The Galaxy platform for accessible, reproducible, and collaborative data analyses: 2024 update](#)³⁶

A web platform for large-scale data analysis that makes high performance compute infrastructures more widely accessible. The main Galaxy server in Europe is [UseGalaxy.eu](#)³⁷. The Galaxy Project fosters open research and reproducibility with sharing of tools, workflows, results, and visualisations. It makes use of RO-Crates for data and workflow export, and it connects with WorkflowHub for workflow import/export. Galaxy also promotes environmental impact awareness by exposing resource usage of the computations launched by the users. Extensive training materials and documentation is offered through the [Galaxy Training Network](#)³⁸.

[Documentation](#) ▾ [Interoperability](#) ▾ [Accessibility/License](#) ▾ [Reproducibility](#) ▾

[DOME Registry](#)³⁹

[DOME: recommendations for supervised machine learning validation in biology](#)⁴⁰

DOME Registry is a collaborative platform designed to promote transparency and reproducibility in machine learning research. Built upon the foundations of the DOME Recommendations, a set of guidelines for reporting machine learning methods in life science

³¹ <http://w3id.org/ro/crate/>

³² <https://doi.org/10.3233/DS-210053>

³³ <http://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.1>

³⁴ <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/background#research-object-background>

³⁵ <https://galaxyproject.org/>

³⁶ <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkae410>

³⁷ <https://usegalaxy.eu>

³⁸ <https://training.galaxyproject.org/>

³⁹ <https://registry.dome-ml.org/intro>

⁴⁰ <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-021-01205-4>

research, the DOME Registry serves as a central repository for curated annotations of machine learning papers. By providing a standardised framework for describing methods and experimental details, the DOME Registry aims to enhance the accessibility, comparability, and overall quality of machine learning research in the life sciences.

[Documentation](#) - [Versioning](#) - [Reproducibility](#) - [Documentation](#) - [Portability](#) -

[BioContainers](#)⁴¹

[BioContainers: an open-source and community-driven framework for software standardisation](#)⁴²

BioContainers is a community-driven project that provides the infrastructure and basic guidelines to create, manage and distribute bioinformatics packages (e.g conda) and containers (e.g docker, singularity). BioContainers is based on the popular frameworks Conda, Docker and Singularity.

[Documentation](#) - [Interoperability](#) - [Accessibility/License](#) - [Reproducibility](#) - [Testing](#) - [Portability](#) - [Sustainability](#) -

[NF-core](#)

[The nf-core framework for community-curated bioinformatics pipelines](#)

[nf-core: Community curated bioinformatics pipelines](#)⁴³

nf-core is a community effort to collect a curated set of annotated analysis pipelines built with Nextflow. It provides an easy way to share, and reuse existing life-science workflows.

[Documentation](#) - [Versioning](#) - [Accessibility/License](#) - [Testing](#) - [Reproducibility](#) - [Portability](#) - [Sustainability](#) -

[proTES](#)⁴⁴

proTES is a scalable API gateway that enhances the GA4GH Cloud ecosystem by facilitating the federation of containerized workloads across diverse environments. Serving as a middleware solution for the GA4GH Task Execution Service (TES), proTES enables seamless integration and interoperability of genomic data processing tasks. By providing features such as load balancing, telemetry collection, and support for OAuth2 authorization, proTES empowers researchers to efficiently manage and share genomic data while adhering to the standards set by the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH). This connection ensures that proTES plays a pivotal role in advancing collaborative research and innovation in precision medicine.

[Documentation](#) - [Interoperability](#) - [Versioning](#) - [Accessibility/License](#) - [Reproducibility](#) - [Portability](#) -

[Bioschemas](#)⁴⁵

[Schema.org for Scientific Data](#)⁴⁶

[Bioschemas: From Potato Salad to Protein Annotation](#)⁴⁷.

⁴¹ <https://biocontainers.pro/>

⁴² <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btx192>

⁴³ <https://doi.org/10.1101/610741>

⁴⁴ <https://github.com/elixir-cloud-aai/proTES>

⁴⁵ <https://bioschemas.org/>

⁴⁶ https://doi.org/10.1142/9789811265679_0027

⁴⁷ <https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-1963/paper579.pdf>

Bioschemas is an initiative aimed at improving the findability of life sciences resources—such as datasets, software, and training materials—by promoting the use of Schema.org markup on websites. This structured markup enhances the indexing of resources by search engines, facilitating their discovery and analysis. Bioschemas contributes to the development of new types and properties within Schema.org specifically for life sciences and defines usage profiles to guide consistent implementation of this markup.

[Interoperability](#) ▾ [Portability](#) ▾ [Sustainability](#) ▾

Training/Lessons

The **Training/Lessons** section offers educational materials aimed at improving knowledge and skills related to research software development. It covers topics such as creating Software Management Plans, understanding licensing options, and implementing open-source practices. These training materials are designed to help researchers and developers enhance the discoverability, reusability, and transparency of their software, fostering better research outcomes.

- [4 Simple recommendations for Open Source Software \(softdev4research.github.io\)](https://softdev4research.github.io)⁴⁸
The lesson aims to improve research software's discoverability, reusability, and transparency through four recommendations. Participants should know GitHub for creating public repositories. The topics include the importance of best practices and Open Source, making source code public from the start, adopting and complying with open source licences, establishing clear contribution and governance processes, and providing metadata to register software in community registries.

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[Recognition](#) ▾ [Sustainability](#) ▾

- [Software Management Plans](#)⁴⁹
The ELIXIR Software Management Plan (SMP) simplifies software management for life science projects, focusing on accessibility and reusability while adhering to FAIR principles. It aids reproducibility, meets funding requirements, and aligns with community standards. Key stakeholders include funders, policy makers, service providers, software managers, and publishers who need SMPs but do not fill them out. Adopters such as developers, principal investigators, and organisations are responsible for creating and using SMPs. Resources include the ELIXIR Software Management Wizard and various template formats. The SMP is updated through community feedback and an editorial process, with details available on GitHub and further reading provided in the BioHackrXiv article.

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[Recognition](#) ▾ [Reproducibility](#) ▾ [Software Management Plan](#) ▾ [Sustainability](#) ▾

- [ELIXIR Software Management Plan Lesson](#)⁵⁰
This lesson guides users through completing a Software Management Plan (SMP),

⁴⁸ <https://softdev4research.github.io/4OSS-lesson/>

⁴⁹ <https://elixir-europe.github.io/software-management-plans/>

⁵⁰ <https://elixir-europe.github.io/elixir-smp-lesson/>

introducing essential concepts and terminology for understanding various stages and technologies involved. "Stages" refer to related aspects of the research software development process, which may overlap and are not necessarily sequential. The lesson caters to various audiences, with profiles available to identify its relevance. It covers starting the plan, construction, application, production, and publication stages, and concludes with a wrap-up and final thoughts.

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[Recognition](#) ▾ [Reproducibility](#) ▾ [Software Management Plan](#) ▾

- [ELIXIR Software Management Plan for Life Sciences](#)⁵¹

ELIXIR Software Management Plan (SMP) for life science researchers, aligned with FAIR principles, to manage the software lifecycle. It provides context and raises awareness, requiring less technical knowledge than existing SMPs. Developed from community feedback, it will evolve into a human- and machine-readable format for integration with ELIXIR Tools. The target audience includes life science researchers and the broader scientific community.

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[Recognition](#) ▾ [Testing](#) ▾ [Software Management Plan](#) ▾ [Sustainability](#) ▾
[Portability](#) ▾

- [EVERSE RSQkit: Research Software Quality kit](#)⁵²

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⁵¹ <https://doi.org/10.37044/osf.io/k8znb>

⁵² <https://everse.software/RSQKit/>

General best practices outside of the ELIXIR infrastructure

This section serves as a reference point for essential best practices and recommendations in developing open-source software and managing research software projects, drawing insights from a variety of sources beyond the ELIXIR infrastructure. The guidelines presented herein reflect the collective expertise and experiences of the broader scientific and software development communities. By incorporating these external best practices, researchers and software developers can enhance the quality, accessibility, and sustainability of their projects, ultimately fostering greater collaboration and impact within the scientific landscape. In the future, tagging or referencing resources endorsed by ELIXIR Communities, FGs, or Nodes would help capture valuable, ELIXIR-relevant tools not currently covered by STEERS. This approach would broaden the resource pool, increase community engagement, and ensure we stay aligned with the evolving contributions within ELIXIR. Regular input from these groups could make the document more comprehensive and dynamic in future versions.

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 9. <https://workflows.community/groups/fair/>
 10. <https://workflowhub.eu/>
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Best Practices for Sustainability

1. [Current Issues in Software Re-Usability: A Critical Review of the Methodological & Legal Issues.](#)
 2. [The Carbon Footprint of Computational Research.](#) *Nature Computational Science*.
 3. [Green Algorithms: Quantifying the Carbon Footprint of Computation.](#) *Advanced Science* 8 (12): 2100707.
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Services/Platforms

1. [GitHub - ossf/wg-best-practices-os-developers: The Best Practices for OSS Developers working group is dedicated to raising awareness and education of secure code best practices for open source developers.](#) (also under software)
 2. [OpenSSF Best Practices Badge Program](#)
 3. [The Turing Way](#)
 4. [codefair.io](#)
 5. [GitHub - ossf/wg-best-practices-os-developers: The Best Practices for OSS Developers working group is dedicated to raising awareness and education of secure code best practices for open source developers.](#)
 6. <https://github.com/corsa-center/oss-documents/blob/main/README.md>
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Training/Lessons

1. "[Software Carpentry.](#)"
2. "Software Carpentries: FAIR Research Software." <https://carpentries-incubator.github.io/fair-research-software/01-fair-research-software.html>.
3. "Research Software Engineering: Software How-Tos." <https://www.bristol.ac.uk/acrc/research-software-engineering/software-howtos/>.
4. "[Best Practices for Maintainers.](#)" Open Source Guides.
5. "[Code Smells and Anti-Patterns: Signs You Need to Improve Code Quality.](#)"